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E-voting Adoption and Challenges of the Advocacy Coalition Framework in selected Western Nations and Somali Oral Poetry: Rethinking Power and Marginality in IT Project Management

Author Details: Alfred Ndi

University of Bamenda ENS Bambili, Bamenda-P.O. Box Bambili, Republic of Cameroon

Email: alfredndi@yahoo.com

Abstract

This paper set out to trace out a number of pathways to address the problem of adopting and diffusing e-voting as a new global model of electoral democracy through an IT project management model. The paper found out that e-voting was beset by numerous challenges. Using data from selected western countries and oral poetry from Somalia, and drawing from the advocacy coalition framework of e-voting, it comes to the conclusion that continental literature and data can be very useful sources of insights for a critical approach to e-voting. The model suggested is not simply a variation of traditional project management that can address the problem of susceptibility to multiple factors such as social division, the erosion of community solidarity and trust, conflict of views between stakeholding coalitions leading to non-adoption of e-voting at national level and relative adoption at sub-national level, the predominance of emotions and fears between coalition groups over substantive issues, risks at different levels of procedure, and informational, financial and institutional constraints of and pressures on e-policy makers.

Keywords

E-voting and elections in wstern democracies; advocacy coalition framework; Somali oral poetry; IT project management, ICT4development.

1.0 Introduction

E-voting (or internet voting: i-voting) is a scheme that is still to be practised in many African nation states. It is being deployed at a limited scale and in some cases successfully in developed nations to generate online election results. When i-voting was introduced, the idea behind it was that it would modernize the classical voting process by facilitating efficiency and access. The expectation too was that it would increase turnout of young voters, facilitate discretion and accessibility for disabled, busy and other voters, reduce voter errors and accidentally compromised ballots, produce faster and more accurate ballot counts and would be environmentally friendly. However, the challenge is that the expansion of digital voting is stalling even in advanced democracies. E-voting trials are being suspended and there is inertia at national levels even though, at sub-national levels, there is an apparent enthusiasm to manage the transition to internet voting and deploy the technology in successful ways (Krimmer et al. eds, 2017) [1]. In addition, there are certain preoccupations, concerns, and questions that have to do with their accuracy and security (Mossberger 2012) [2]. The issue now is not whether electronic voting machines will acquire universal application and become the standard voting instrument but how they can be made to become accurate and secured (Ibid). The problem now is that the electronic system of voting has the potential to discriminate against computer ‘illiterates’ and people who have limited skills in a computer such as the elderly and the poor. The problem of the ‘digital divide’ (cf. Ndi 2017) [3] is clearly a context that can bring back the prospect of universally deploying the electronic voting machine. Whether during the 2008 social media-based Obama election campaign or the 2011 political revolutions and civic protest movements of the Arab Spring movement, the recent past has been characterized by a complex and extensive shift in the political landscape, as Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, blogs and other participatory platforms extended the spaces for political communication and activism (Elmer, Langlois and McKelvey 2012) [4]. But with the advent of these channels, has come the need for a permanent networked campaign, a constant readiness to concentrate on political instances, crises and elections not only in nation states like the U.S.A., Canada and Australia but also in the Third World. There is an explosion in the number of new political communicators and actors such as advocacy groups, political bloggers, diverse publics, and staff of political

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parties that are engaged in political maneuvering in different participatory platforms. So, there are constant attempts to manage the *plurality* of voices that mark contemporary politics.

Yet, despite this evidence, the Norwegian government declared in 2014 that it was ending e-voting trials because there were concerns over privacy issues and over the question of turnout by youths (Krimmer et al. eds, 2017) [1]. The UK government ended its own online voting pilots in 2004 because of fears of insecurity of the votes and low turnout (Ibid). There is a lack of progress toward generalized online voting even in democracies of the West. Digital voting appears to have stalled while the deployment of the technology for voter identification and registration, and electronic counting of paper ballots has increased. After adoption in 2000 in many nation states like the USA, UK, Canada, Estonia, Mexico, India, Panama, France, and Switzerland, there was a general termination of pilot studies for reasons of technical considerations and failure to see expected turnout effects. Online voting is not used at the national level in many of these nation states but at sub-national and local levels for reasons of failure to meet expectations in voter participation, possibilities of fraud and pressures to ensure that verification instruments determine whether effective i-voting reflected the original intention of e-voters. Other factors like the decline in trust and budget crises of nation states delayed commitment to trials of the digital technology. The challenge now is how do we comprehend this apparent *impasse* and how do we take e-voting out of this *stasis* where public debates over it run on well-worn lines? A number of studies have been done that locate e-voting in its intersection with theoretical paradigms to explain why some nation states are more advanced than others in reforming policies on the adoption of digital technology, accounting for security assurances, and so forth. Damgard, Groth and Salomonsen investigate e-voting and security with regard to homomorphic encryption in Gritzalis's (2003) work titled *Secure Electronic Voting* [5]. From the viewpoint of comparative analysis, e-voting is studied by Maurer and Barat. eds, (2016) [6], *E-voting Case Law: A Comparative Analysis*, in terms of legal instruments employed to regulate the technology in nation states like Germany, Australia, Brazil, France, Argentina, Estonia, and India. Following on their footsteps, Kersting and Baldersheim, (2004) [7] in their work *Electronic Voting And Democracy: A Comparative Analysis*, are concerned with issues of legitimacy and as well as practical concerns over why e-voting is driving certain nation states toward adoption faster than others. Engaging the discussion from the perspective of actor-network *theory* (ANT), Ryan and Shoemakers (2009) [8], prefer to concentrate on social dynamics in the formation of autonomous relationships between man and machine. Chaume et al.'s (2010) [9] *Towards Trustworthy Elections: New Directions In Electronic Voting*, employ the information paradigm to investigate the recurrent theme of trust in the treatment of e-voting electoral results, while a similar thematic is treated in a book edited by Sideridis et al. (2013) [10] as *E-Democracy, Security, Privacy And Trust In A Digital World*, by drawing from insights in proceedings of a post-conference of the 5th International Conference on privacy, security and trust in a digital world, e-democracy, organized in Athens, Greece, December 2013.

This paper sets out to investigate an IT project management protocol for e-voting in developing African countries by drawing insights from a continental discourse, namely, Somali oral poetry. Exploiting the advocacy coalition paradigm of e-voting from a critical lens perspective, the paper argues that the tacit insights of oral poetry can enlighten policy makers to rethink new ways of adopting and practising the expansion of the technology in nation states but with a sensitivity to developing contexts. It provides a template from which any further research in this direction can draw inspiration to emerge with a thorough checklist of painpoints to iron out before effective e-voting practice can be triggered off in developing nation states like those in Africa. This paper draws comparative insights from the advocacy coalition framework developed by Paul Sabatier and public policy scholars to investigate why online voting stalls in selected e-political contexts of nation states such as Canada and Australia (Krimmer et al. eds, 2017) [1] and Somalia. It proposes specific insights from data culled from Krimmer et al.'s (2017) *Electronic voting: First international joint conference, e-vote-ID 2016, Bregenz, Austria, October 18-21, proceesings*, labeled as Table 1: The well established remote online voting debate (page 165), Table 2: Remote online voting in Canadian municipal elections (page 167), Table 3: Elections using internet voting in New South Wales (page 172), In each of these nation states in the West and in Africa, the policy adoption and practice orientations of internet voting, based on the advocacy coalition

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framework, involve relatively closed and small groups of experts in various fields of specialization. These experts and fields include policy makers, law courts, the media, political party candidates and members, computer technologists, internet security experts, parliamentary commissions on electoral issues, communities of persons living in geographically enclaved areas and advocacy groups for persons with disabilities, which are also confronted with postmodernist struggles with rights as illustrated in non-western nation state contexts (Ndi 2012) [12].

2.0 Methodology

As Johnson (1974) [13] has instructed us, the performance of Somali oral poetry, the Cushitic nations of the Horn of Africa, is not restricted only to formal occasions and specific audiences but extensible to political and social debates. The most recent genre to develop out of the marginalized segments of Somalia referred to by the explorer Sir Burton in 1855, as a nation of poets, is the *hees* or *heellooyin*, which is chanted by youths and women. In these societies, oral poetry is deployed as an act of communication and defiance between individuals in the realms of power and marginalized groups, communities or other stakeholders. This versified communication is conducted in contexts that are socially volatile and delicate because sensitive issues are discussed about the inclusion/exclusion of stakeholders from the structures of power. The message is often veiled so that all the stakeholders can understand the state of their relationships with one another. Normally the performing artists do not authority to chastise, but this old verse tradition gives them the chance to air their opinions during a public occasion. In one of those public occasions (Johnson 1974: 123-125), a junior announcer in Radio Muqdisho is assigned the task of covering parliamentary elections for the position of President of the Republic. From the gallery where the announcer plays out his *heellooyin* verses on loudspeakers placed at various corners of the hall, the announcer can see the vote stakeholders, namely, the electronic voting board members, the contenders, the parliamentarians, the incumbent President Aadan Cabdulle Cismaan, the radio audience and the others. As the voting goes on, the verses are being played out on loudspeakers to the hearing of the voters, the parliamentarians and everyone in the country. When the results of the electronic voting are pronounced, there is no majority candidate. In the next caucus, there is more musical poetry, and after the vote, there is again no majority. Still, in the next one once more, the journalist takes out a cassette and plays the popular entertainment song called *leexo*, as follows:

Innakoo laamaane ah! While we were yet together
Iyo laba naf-quaybsile, Helping one other in every way,
Talo geed ko laashee, you cast good counsel away to the top of a high tree!
Adigaa is lumiyo, you caused yourself distress,
Isu loogay cadoowgow, and slaughtered yourself for your enemy,
Libintaadin siiyee giving your victory to him,
Waadigan se litee now, you are so weakened,
Leexadu koo sidatee that light breezes bear you up,
Had ba laan cuskanayee and from time to time, you grasp at a branch.
Liibanteed adduunyada for all the pleasures of this earth,
Ruux na laasan maayee one cannot fully enjoy,
Maxaa luray naftadii tell me, what causes you this distress?

Waa laac adduunyadu The world is but a mirage,
Labadii walaloo ah, And for every two brothers,
Mid ba maalin ladanyoo only one being happy each day,
Ruuxii u liil-galay The one who is fortunate
La ma loolo dhereggoo should not abuse his property,
Luggooyada ma geystee should not maltreat his neighbour
Waadigan se labtiyo and in your case however,

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Lugaha is la waayaye your breast and feet are out of accord
Meel sare lalanaye for you are drifting up, up into the air,
Liibaanteed adduunyada For all the pleasures of this earth,
Ruux na laasan maayen one cannot fully enjoy
Maxaa luraay naaftadii tell me what causes you this distress?
Aniga ba laftiyo jiidh Behold my flesh and all my bones,
Waakii yi laastan were completely consumed by him,
Liqi waayee oontee I cannot even swallow food,
Adigaa lis caanood the abundance of milk
Iyo laad xareediyo pure rainwater
Laydhiyo ladh diidee fresh air, and the rest in the cool shade: the rest you have rejected
Waadigan sidii liigh it is you, who like the male *garanuug*,
Laasimay ugaadhee left the (other) game, and
Waclada u leexdee turned o a desolate place
Liibaanteed addunyaada For all the pleasures of this earth
Ruux na laasan maayen one cannot fully enjoy
Maxaa luraay naaftadii tell me what causes you this distress?

Daaxaad ladnaan rays so often in the prosperity of the rains,
Sidaad aar libax taay as though you were a proud lion,
Taalaabada ladhaysoo you walked about majestically
Anna lahashadaadii whilst I, because of your carousing,
Ledi waayo ciil loo had sleepless nights from impotent anger
Liidnimo i raacdee And sometimes behaved like a fool,
Lallabaa habeenkiyo the beacon fire in the night
Malibdaan jacay loo and love, they never disappear
Waalaleg doodan they roll on after you, unrestrained,
Liibaanteed addunyaada For all the pleasures of this earth
Ruux na laasan maayen one cannot fully enjoy
Maxaa luraay naaftadii tell me what causes you this distress?

Innakoo laamaane ah! While we were yet together
Iyo laba naf-quaybsile, Helping one other in every way,
Talo geed ko laashee, you cast good counsel away to the top of a high tree!
Adigaa is lumiyo, you caused yourself distress,
Isu loogay cadoowgow, and slaughtered yourself for your enemy,
Libintaadin siiyee giving your victory to him,
Waadigan se litee now, you are so weakened,
Leexadu koo sidatee that light breezes bear you up,
Had ba laan cuskanayee and from time to time, you grasp at a branch.
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Maxaa luraay naaftadii tell me what causes you this distress?

Johnson, 1995: 115-117, "Power, marginality and Somali oral poetry: case studies in the dynamics of tradition")

3.0 Results

When the results were pronounced, the word that came out was that the poem *leexo* had brought down the government of Aadan Cabdulle Cisman and the new president was Dr. Cabdi-rashiid Cali Shar Ma Arke. But

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beyond the respective results, the verse and the data based on Somalia's oral tradition and on selected western democracies are very instructive on the fundamental question of implementation of the e-voting system, which is threatened by a deep gulf between societal members. The challenge for its adoption is in understanding the postmodern discourses of division that its effective application has to deal with. Michel de Certeau elaborated in his book entitled *The Practice of Everyday Life*, that the ways in which groups and communities of people attempt to individualize mass culture, by changing the Foucauldian 'order of things', from utilitarian objects (such as e-voting machines) to new forms of rituals, language, laws, street programmes, etc. so as to appropriate them as their own (or their non-own) is intriguing. The book re-examines related paradigms from Kant, Wittgenstein to Dtienne, Foucault and Bourdieu and its insights enable us to reconsider how society is structured out critically. The social sciences investigate society in terms of language, traditions, art, symbols and articles of exchange that constitute a given culture; however, they lack a formal method of examining how groups, people and individuals re-appropriate their culture in everyday situations. De Certeau's book enables us to see that in the public activities of re-use of products, services, brands, etc., resides a lot of opportunities for marginalized groups, communities and people, like those in Somalia, to subvert the institutional ideologies that powerful groups seek to impose upon the rest. It is important to comprehend how such deconstructive activities as in the *leexo* verses, show us a truer and living picture of people not merely as static, robotic compliers, but rather, as creators, artists and producers. People are not simply passive *cyborgs* subjected to received technological cultures; they are not merely 'consumers' but 'users' who craft out new tactics of interaction. Institutions such as governments, corporations, technological platforms, scientific enterprise, the state, municipality, etc., are structures of power that 'produce' products or services using rules and regulations, while individuals, groups and communities are not simply coalitions of 'consumers,' advocating for the products, but actors like a street walker moving in tactical ways, taking shortcuts, undetermined by plans, etc.

The data and verse prioritize not merely what de Certeau sees as the 'repressive' or power aspect of modern society, namely, the e-voting technology, but more especially the 'arts of doing,' the elements of creative resistance by ordinary people, their tactics in what they see as a battle of repression and expression. The poem opens up with the context of the advocacy coalition paradigm of e-voting set out as an ideal framework that provides insights on how e-voting processes - trials, effective elections, etc. – can be conducted to success. However, as the verse unfolds and as the data show, there are serious areas of peril in the deployment of this paradigm for effective implementation of online voting in nation state contexts of e-politics. These areas have to do with changes in the mindset of communities over the course of different time periods, civic engagement, participation, and relationships. We start off with the vulnerability of the framework to time periods. A critical understanding of the reasons why, despite its potentials, the advocacy coalition framework of e-voting is very susceptible to the power crisis, stalling and value disintegration, must consider shifts in people's mindset from a community spirited to an individualistic and self-sufficient attitude. The online technology came at a historical time of the autonomous self-satisfying vision of individuals, as versified by the *leexo* poems, and this optimized its vulnerability to the passage of time. At the end of the Nineteenth century, for example, groups and communities in Western societies encouraged values such as civic engagement and participation in activities of interest to all. Labour unions, churches, and clubs were created in Canada, Australia, the US, etc., where service organizations such as the *Rotary Club* and the *Kiwanis* set up local and state branch chapters and national offices paralleling the US government's *three-tier* format (Putnam 2000, Skocpol and Firorina, eds, 1999) [13]. But what is critical here is that these organizations drew their strength not only from *loyalty* and *trust* at a local level but also from strong connections with international communities. From the 1880s to 1920s, these multi-tiered organizations expanded and group life became the foundation for civil societies in the 1960s in the US, for example. But from the 1960s to the present day, multi-tiered organizations declined seriously at unprecedented rates and were replaced by advocacy associations with a professional orientation (376). These advocacy coalition frameworks are now eclipsing old, hierarchical organizations that were strung together by solidarity and community values to address certain critical issues of society. The glue that holds together groups of teachers, lawyers, the clergy and another expert to address issues like violence in schools is no longer as

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powerful as the long-term trust and loyalty that communities had in hierarchical structures with potent connections to diverse constituencies. Consequently, with the passage of time, the importance of these issues which were still serious, started to recede as group solidarity started to dwindle and erode even with re-surfacing of fresh issues needing the forging of robust cross-organizational coalitions. So, coalitions came and went off, were created and disappeared as the relationships between individuals in groups became very loose, *ad hoc* and sporadic. Although people still have ties with community groups, they do not partake in activities that demand from them a lot of time and enduring loyalty.

Today, in our highly self-interested, modern world, individuals league up with other individuals to address emerging issues like gun threats to school children, urban banditry, etc. They maintain friendships through emails, greeting cards, visits, phone calls, etc. The internet is now employed to galvanize citizens to advance, for example, a nation state political cause. There is no doubt that people gain a sense of belonging from such relationships; however, unlike in the past, present-day relationships are loose, and less binding on people; the acquaintances are superficial, the contacts sporadic and the commitments shifting. With the increasing pre-eminence of the individualist attitude as opposed to the communal spirit of the past, the sense of civic engagement necessary to address questions of adoption and practice of e-voting is now eroded. The modern context of the consumer economy, fast food, vacations, entertainment business, etc., is abundant with the language of *self-interest*, *self-pleasure* and the imperative of *personal happiness*. The present context of self-gratification that the poet decries has submerged the past context of community sharing and service and placed prospects of technological diffusion and adoption for democratic deliberation at bay. As a direct result of this passage of time but also an uncritical reliance by Canada and Australia on the advocacy coalition framework of e-voting, these nation states became susceptible to and witnessed a major *impasse* with the online voting debate as the digital technology was rejected at the nation state level of elections and accepted mainly at the sub-national levels where there is still a limited degree of the community solidarity of old. The vulnerability of the advocacy framework at the nation state opened up a site of contestation where proponents and opponents of deliberative democracy exchanged diametrically varying opinions about online voting. Consequently, against the background of self-referentiality and egocentricism of the new context, a debate (Krimmer et al. eds, 2017, *Electronic voting: First international joint conference, e-vote-ID 2016, Bregenz, Austria, October 18-21, proceedings*, Table 1) [1], has emerged over the feasibility of online voting frameworks on issues such as accessibility, the need to take precaution by holding back so that other nation states should first go ahead and take the electoral risks in the use of electronic media, lack of full information, absence of scrutiny of ballot count, lack of secrecy owing to factors like coercion, family pressure, vote buying, and vote interception, erosion of social voting rituals, and lack of voter education.

There are three pathways through which a gridlock can emerge between opposing groups of proponents on the online voting machinery of democracy when the digital advocacy paradigm is applied. First, a financial depression may cause a nation state government to reduce aid to innovation in an electoral system like e-voting, or there may be a breakdown in the electronic voting process which advantages a side of the policy argument (Ibid: 166). Second, accumulated learning of practical examples and of new information that is oriented toward policy adoption may endorse the view of one of the coalitions over another coalition. Third, a compromise may emerge from the realization that the policy *status quo* is unfavourable to each of the opposing views. In this case, there is no need for them to compete because their interests coalesce into a possible alliance. The first two pathways are sites of intersection that are responsible for the growing disinterest of Canada and Australia in the promotion of the online voting policy (Ibid). Consequently, these national state governments, as a stakeholder in the advocacy paradigm, dread the prospect that the deployment of this digital technology may engender electoral results which they may be compelled to invalidate later on. On the other hand, opposing stakeholders of coalition groups point to the low turnouts of youthful voters as a countervailing reason for policy makers to freeze any intention to adopt. So, the first two pathways account for very potent reasons why policy deciders in Canada and Australia have failed to adopt and apply e-voting at the nation state level (Ibid).

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Unlike at the nation state level, where the challenges are huge and have caused policy makers to withdraw prospects of adoption and practice, at the sub-national level, there is a more committed and growing involvement to varying degrees. As the data show, in 2003, 192 municipal elections were organized in Canada in the Ontario province with remote online voting (cf. Table 2: Remote online voting in Canadian municipal elections) (Ibid: 167). The number of councils deploying i-poll technology even doubled with each election. So, from the 2003 electoral year, about 4.5 million online voting opportunities were created in council elections (Ibid). Even when options of telephone or paper were made available, digital voting was increasingly popular among Ontario voters in the 2014 local elections. For example, in 23 councils that provided three voting methods, 12.8% voted via telephone, 31.6% via paper and 55.6% cast their votes through the internet (Ibid:170). In the 2010 council elections deploying the three methods of paper, telephone and internet, internet voting was more popular than the combination of telephone and paper balloting combined in 8 out of 12 municipalities, more popular than either of the two methods of voting in 3 councils and less popular than both only in a single municipality. More than 90% of online voters were satisfied in these elections and express their desire to see digital voting expand into other provincial and federal elections. They confied that they would continue to employ digital technology in future elections.

The western online voters were persuaded that the digital mode of elections is convenient, although there were concerns over accessibility. 14% of the Ontario digital voters affirmed that they might never have voted if the option of digital voting was not made available to them (Ibid: 170). In 2014, 58% of e-voters who declared they did not vote via the internet mode in 2010 confirmed that accessibility to the digital option was the chief reason for adopting this positive behaviour (Ibid). After the policy adoption of the digital voting reform, a 3% increase in turnout was registered (Ibid). Clearly, online voting has the potential to persuade a new flux of non-committed voters to engage. The adoption of electoral reforms by policy makers caused political candidates to try hard to persuade voters to align with the digital mode and behavioral practices. Political candidates at this level are convinced that e-voting would increase the turnout of youths and would augment their participation and interest in the new digital culture of elections. 89% of the municipal candidates endorsed the advent of i-voting as a platform of democratic deliberation; nevertheless, about 64% of them objected to the deployment of digital technology as the only electoral channel (Ibid). Nevertheless, in the province of Alberta, e-voting was suspended for reason of policy shock in 2012, Edmonton's officials agreed to adopt e-voting, a consultation process was triggered through opinion surveys, citizen roundtables, mock elections and the creation and enforcement of a Citizen's Jury. The Jury voted in favour of i-voting for the upcoming 2013 elections after considering the arguments of experts. However, when the decision came before the city council for approval and adoption, a computer programmer confessed before it that the digital system was unsafe because he voted twice in the mock elections that were conducted. This testimony optimized doubts about the security of the internet voting system and resulted in a voting score of 11 to 2 in disfavor of adoption (Ibid: 171). The Minister of municipal affairs for Alberta enforced a moratorium against the use of internet voting for the 2013 elections and this triggered the same attitudes and official policy measures in other municipalities. Thus, from the shock of a security compromise even in a mock election exercise, the electronic voting system can suffer an adverse decision in policies of adoption and practice.

In the Australian example, data show that New South Wales is the only jurisdiction out of six states that were able to adopt a policy of e-voting and voters deployed the iVote(R) System. The data show that from 2011 about 339.000 voters cast their votes across nine electoral periods (Table 3: Elections using internet voting in New South Wales) (Ibid:172). Comparatively, online voting is available to voters in Canadian municipalities whereas only certain categories of voters can employ the electronic vote in New South Wales. The goals of policy makers in both nation state contexts are not the same. Whereas in the case of Canada, the goal is to increase the turnout of youths in the municipality elections, the goal of policy makers in New South Wales is not increase of turnout but increase in access to the elections for citizens who otherwise would find it impossible to participate from their remote areas for reasons of visual impairment, physical disability, travel, illiteracy, etc. (Ibid: 171-172). E-voting channels are available in New South Wales in addition to postal voting,

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mobile voting and others. Policy makers are incentivized to support i-voting because it is the only way to facilitate convenience for these categories of voters, whose number is on the increase as they are also calling on other municipalities to enforce the e-voting reform. The foundation stone of democracy is voting, so the increasingly strong belief is that there is no point in enforcing democracy if votes will not be counted or *shown* to be effectively counted. The problem with the advocacy coalition framework of e-voting is that its potential is also its weakness. The same political party members, computer technologists, internet security experts, parliamentary commissions on electoral issues, city juries, persons living in geographically enclaved areas, advocacy groups for persons with physical or other disabilities, etc. that the framework prescribes are the same that can subvert its potentials in e-voting. These advocacy groups raise the stakes by investing in *emotions* when they debate on the deployability of e-voting technology (Machlis, 2004) [14]. For example, with the advent of e-commerce technology, the same *fears* of feasibility emerged as opponents argued that the digital transactions were unsafe. *Fear* became a factor more critical than advocacy groups, experts, politicians or policy makers. However, early web retailers overcame these fears and argued that encrypted credit card data transmitted through the internet was safer than giving one's card to a waitress. But *allaying fears* was not enough. Digital marketing strategies were also employed to raise awareness that no one would be liable to fraud if they brought products online; consequently, online consumers started to regain confidence. Consumers started to 'test the waters' by making small purchases from trusted brands. They were willing to attempt again as soon as they discovered that their credit data and identities were not stolen (Ibid).

The challenge, therefore, is *how to persuade* stakeholders in the advocacy coalition framework to *rethink their judgments* on the use of the e-voting machine as a successful practice. The generation of 'paper-trails' is an important factor in the persuasion and rethinking of negative judgments. Even when stakeholders in the advocacy coalition such as officials of elections hire security teams to train poll workers on security questions, test their apparatuses, create procedures of auditing and carry out random tests on the electronic system, all of this principally technical work does not leave any trace behind to persuade e-voting skeptics that the system is secure. It is still not enough for experts to report that a digital voting system is hard to hack into or to state that the possibility of hampering is very low. The end-user of any new technology is critical for its success such as the case of e-voting, which is a disruptive technology. All are in the *psychoanalysis*: the more controversial the digital technology is, the more it would be needful to persuade users by showing how they would benefit by generating 'print outs' as security evidence. Gasoline pumps and ATMs issue receipts, so it should be possible for an e-voting system to possess reliable printing machines. Modernization in democracy also means that voters should be given options of paper or touch screen balloting, as this would only give them greater confidence in the ideological system of democracy (Ibid). But even this evidentiary analysis does not tell the whole story. Prior to the 2004 US elections, a series of issues were raised with 'paper-trails' and print out evidence. Candidate's camps such as the Republican and Democratic parties were raising concerns over electronic voting machines, the need for paper ballots in the event of a recount, calls for everyone to order their absentee ballots and so on (Alvarez and Hall 2008) [15]. Appeals were made for voting absentee so that in case of a close vote, it would be possible to retrieve a physical copy of the vote and protect one's right to vote. In Florida, for example, absentee ballots were used in order to avoid direct recording equipment machines. The voters were informed that by voting absentee, a paper record would be kept and this would be counted. However, 58,000 votes were lost after they left the election office in Broward County (Ibid). Voters who opted to vote absentee could not find their names on the list, could not vote in any other ways and not receive a replacement absentee ballot at a time when it could be returned and counted. In this way, many voters were disfranchised by the electronic voting debate mobilizing the electorate because absentee voting and its complexities were not thoughtfully considered. Thus, beyond just the stakeholding of advocacy coalitions, there are numerous *risks* at different levels of procedure, voter errors in filling out forms, deadlines, media framing of debates and public perception, and so forth. The advocacy coalition framework for e-voting appears to present an ideal picture of stakeholders but ignores the fact the coalition stakeholders in nation states like state policy makers, are confronted with *constraints* of varying types, namely, inadequate information, insufficient staff and

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inadequate financial resources, etc. than local policy makers (Niemi and Dyck, eds, 2014: 315) [16]. In addition, nation states face institutional restraints like balancing budgets, term limitations and pressure from federal administrations (Ibid) that may compromise *solidarity* between coalition stakeholders. Voters who stay outside their nation state when elections are organized are confronted with huge difficulties to exercise their democratic rights. There is always an absence of practical arrangements and procedures to facilitate external voting. With an increase in the rate of migration and the extension of democracy, there is growing interest in new questions of voting rights for citizens who are absent from their own countries.

4.0 Discussion

In the light of the complexities that the data in western democracies and African continental literature have portrayed so well, we suggest that any IT project management for e-voting should consider certain criteria for enforcement. First, the planning stage should be detailed on how each activity will be carried out, the persons who will be assigned different tasks, and the resources that will be needed. All the stakeholders must be stated, with a timeline given and the needed budget is drawn. A communication system should be established to communicate with customers, employees, government, shareholders within and outside the country. The firm needs information from these stakeholders and information should flow thanks to the development of an information technology system freely. The planning stage is actually a blueprint of activities that should be implemented, the financing of the project and other information that can enable a project manager to familiarize themselves with all the activities and steps to be enforced to certain the project is successful. The planning has to detail all the requirements, stipulate all the activities necessary to achieve the objective of a successful e-voting programme, the entire schedule and the possible budget that would be needed to execute, monitor and control the project (Fioravanti 2006). [17] It can integrate and strengthen subsidiary plans and baselines from the planning process. It can describe what should be executed, how this should be implemented, when, etc. The information system should eliminate current communication problems in society. It should move from traditional business communication methods e.g., letters to suppliers (good though for facilitating documentation for future reference), memos pinned on the notice board for the attention of employees, to a communication system that prioritizes speed and efficiency. Therefore, its system should be automated so that documents are submitted or received electronically. This way, any classified message is delivered only to the intended person.

A clear management structure with a definition of how every activity will be executed and the individuals responsible. But the project manager must also know some of the challenges that the project comes to solve, determine how best these factors can be put together to realize the result in the project (Kerzner 2009). [18] It may outsource the technical workforce to execute the project while internalizing the process so that after the departure of these outsourced officers, the employees can run the new system prospectively. The outsourced firm will have to explain the technical details such as the operational and troubleshooting tasks. The problem or needs have to be identified (Phillips 2004), [19] specifying what is needed to optimize operations. This way, it becomes possible to know what should be carried out in order to ensure that the current operations are enhanced through improved systems. A clear timeline for the activities will be a constant reminder to all the parties involved in what they are expected to achieve within specific schedules ((Marchewka 2009, Schwalbe, 2010. Thomsett 2002). [20] The Gantt chart can be used to specify the activities that will be carried out in this e-project as follows:

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Time 2010	January	February	March	April
<i>Project activity</i> Setting up an e-voting system in an imaginary country				
1. Project planning				
Development of project proposal	Integrate various stakeholders, parliamentarians, contenders, e-voting board, media, ordinary voters from different political parties, etc., as specified by Somalian oral poetry and western data			
Approval of the project proposal	x			
Employment of team members	x			
2. Development and testing	x	x		
Requirements detailed on <i>risks</i> at different levels of procedure, the erosion of community solidarity and trust, the predominance of emotions and fears between coalition groups, conflict of views between stakeholding coalitions leading to prospect of non-adoption of e-voting at national level and relative adoption at sub-national level, and informational, financial and institutional constraints of and pressures on e-policy makers		Ibid: integrates factors like trust, fear, risk, etc,		
Development of prototype	x	x		
Approval of prototype	x	x		
Development of version		x	x	
Testing of the version		x	x	
Application of version correction		x	x	
Approval final version		x	x	
3. Enforcement		x	x	
Training of users			x	x
Rolling out the final version			x	x

In this model of IT project management, management is enabled by Web 2.0 technologies like blogs, wikis, collaborative software, etc., which can now facilitate the distribution of virtual teams to work together efficiently. It is an ideological shift from project management as control () to project management 2.0 as distributed collaboration, leadership and open communication ().

Conclusion

This paper set out to trace out a number of pathways to address the problem of adopting and diffusing e-voting as a new global model of electoral democracy through an IT project management model. The paper found out that e-voting was beset by numerous challenges. Using data from selected western countries and oral poetry from Somalia, and drawing from the advocacy coalition framework of e-voting, it comes to the conclusion that continental literature and data can be very useful sources of insights for a critical approach to e-voting. The model suggested is not simply a variation of traditional project management. But a separate methodology that can be applied not only to small but big projects as well. The model deploys Web 2.0 tools not as islands of technology, but as integrative technologies that can enable collaboration across multiple project teams. These recommendations apply not only to developed societies but also to developing nation states like Somalia, whose *leexo* poetry was used as a pedagogical tool to supply insights for the paper’s findings. In fact, they should be prioritized if the goals of ICTs for development are to be achieved in developing countries (Avgerou 2010) [21].

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The first suggestion is that votes cast on digital technology can be documented by local electronic computers or servers so that they can be checked out for proof of tampering, sabotage, viruses, etc. before being forwarded to the centralized system of computers. The subset of this suggestion is the deployment of an operated closed net or publicly chartered system that can be accessed through electronic machines located in secured rooms in places such as community centres, colleges, universities, schools and libraries with staff that work during the voting day and time. The problem of accessibility during the voting day and time can be resolved by the staff who can take the electronic machines to locations with residents who are unable to travel to vote in election sites. The closed net electronic system is good because of its ease of use, ease of voting and ease of results tallying. After the day and time of voting is over, these machines can then convey data electronically to the ‘democracy computer’ system that tallies and tabulates vote results. The machines and data must be checked out for irregularities like a virus before data is conveyed to the central apparatus. The second sub-set of the model as a solution is for the electronic machine to be programmed to print out two cards immediately when the voter pushes the button to cast or send his vote. These cards which are similar to ballot cards, are bar-coded or punched appropriately and must indicate details on how the voter voted. The voter drops one of the two cards in the ballot box and keeps the other card for his own records. In the event where the election results are disputed or are in doubt, the ‘paper trail’ would be employed to check out the electronic results at random in any individual voting station.

The second suggestion to address the security concerns of electronic voting cards is that the cards can be fitted with PINS as one can find out with credit cards and ATMs, for the sake of ensuring that there is a satisfactory record. A more sophisticated system may consider encoding devices that automatically identify individual owners of the cards with their voices, fingerprints, eye pupil patterns, etc. the sub-set of this solution is to lobby for ‘paper-trails’ because e-voting machines can keep records of each vote cast. This option is an improved version of the soft-ware only system with doubtful recount potential given that such a recount process would require a human agency with the prospect of corruption, manipulation, etc. and further mistrust in the voting electorates. The third suggestion starts with the premise that direct deliberative e-democracy cannot be stopped because of computer illiteracy or lack of skills in the use of technology. Illiteracy cannot and should not stop the institution of universal suffrage and expansion of democracy across the world. The appropriate remedy then is to start off with campaigns of literacy and effective education in the e-voting process and the use of the electronic machine (108). The proponents of direct deliberative e-democracy have to take more aggressive and robust measures to overcome problems of deficiency of skills and illiteracy. At a larger societal level, the paper suggests that there is a need to respond to Putnam’s (2000) [13] call for the development of greater social capital as a strategy to encourage the growth of values in intensive civic engagements. Civic values are necessary to facilitate cooperative activities, like e-voting in e-politics, by developing problem-solving techniques in conversation with another individual who is determined to meet challenges and succeed. The present era of long working hours, the urban sprawl, television entertainment, family pressures and the passage of time from the Second World War epoch when solidarity was necessary to meet the challenges of winning the war, to today’s carefree world of liberty, signify that a project like digital voting requires not just technological but also sociological investment in human values.

Election reform in terms of e-voting is a digital project of contemporary society that is very necessary but also very complex. Its complexity is a result of the fact that the new voting system presents with security and other flaws, which are confusing. However, these flaws should not deter policy makers from adopting e-voting but should be scientifically identified, thoroughly analysed and then addressed in robust ways. This paper is an initial example of how one can accomplish this task. Legislation should be revisited so that it can align with the constantly changing voting technology; for example, legal recourse should be included for improperly counted votes. Regulatory questions and public policy issues on voting technologies should be constantly reviewed. New studies should be carried out not only from legal, technological or security perspectives but also from a historical viewpoint so that the digital system of voting can become more sensitive to what people want and therefore more reliable, accurate, and secure in responding to their needs (Ellis and

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Wall 2007, Kwak, Shah and Holbert 2004, Newton 2001) [22]. In digital technology, people should come first, and machines after. This is the way to ensure the long term sustainability of machines. This paper has shown that electronic voting machinery has potential in politics. The examples of adoption and practice taken from the Canadian and Australian urban contexts are quite illuminating. However, these potentials are compromisable at the level of application in context. Drawing from the e-voting paradigm of advocacy coalition, the paper demonstrates that i-voting is very susceptible to multiple factors such as *risks* at different levels of procedure, the erosion of community solidarity and trust, the predominance of emotions and fears between coalition groups over substantive issues, conflict of views between stakeholding coalitions leading to non-adoption of e-voting at national level and relative adoption at sub-national level, and informational, financial and institutional constraints of and pressures on e-policy makers. Further investigations need to be carried out in other paradigmatic areas of e-voting such as the diffusion of innovation, the voting equilibria perspective, the security and systems theory and so forth.

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Sketch biography

Alfred Ndi holds a *Doctorat d'État* Degree in Postcolonial digital humanities with a specialized interest in continental literature. He investigates the hypertext not only in the *praxis/theory* of digital marketing of space where race, class, ethnicity, gender, sexuality, generation, disability, nation, etc are regular staples but also in the power/ knowledge dynamics of ICT political economy. His long term aim is to develop critical archival databases adapted to all cultural, developmental and relationship discourses for outreach educational purposes that can contribute to the foundations of global peace.

He has published papers on the building, breaking and sharing strategies of critical studies in many academic journals and books.